

Deep-water Calliostomatidae (Vetigastropoda, Gastropoda) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain

Calliostomatidae (Vetigastropoda, Gastropoda) de aguas profundas de la cadena de montañas submarinas del sur de las Azores

Serge GOFAS*,¹ & Leon HOFFMAN**

Recibido el 29-X-2019. Aceptado el 13-I-2020

ABSTRACT

Seven species of the family Calliostomatidae collected on the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC) have been studied. Two species, probably restricted to bathyal crests and slopes of the SASC, are described as new: *Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. and *Calliostoma cyrtoidea* n. sp. Two uncommon species were found as empty shells: *Calliostoma grimaldii* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896 and *Calliostoma normani* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897). *Calliostoma heugteni* Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003 is common on the SASC. *Calliostoma maurolici* (G. Seguenza, 1876) and *Calliostoma leptophyma* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896, which are common in cold-water coral habitats in the NE Atlantic including the SASC, were also collected.

RESUMEN

Se han estudiado siete especies de la familia Calliostomatidae recolectadas en la cadena de montañas submarinas de las Azores del Sur (SASC). Dos especies, probablemente restringidas a las crestas y pendientes batiales del SASC, se describen como nuevas: *Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. y *Calliostoma cyrtoidea* n. sp. Se encontraron conchas vacías de dos especies poco comunes: *Calliostoma grimaldii* Dautzenberg y H. Fischer, 1896 y *Calliostoma normani* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897). *Calliostoma heugteni* Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003 es común en el SASC. También se recolectaron *Calliostoma maurolici* (G. Seguenza, 1876) y *Calliostoma leptophyma* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896, que son comunes en los hábitats de coral de agua fría en el Atlántico nororiental, incluido el SASC.

KEY WORDS: *Calliostoma*, Mollusca, NE Atlantic, bathyal, new species, taxonomy.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Calliostoma*, Mollusca, Atlántico NE, batial, nuevas especies, taxonomía.

INTRODUCTION

This paper reviews the Calliostomatidae encountered in sediment samples gathered during the cruises SEAMOUNT 2 (GOFAS, 1993), POS397 (GEORGE, 2010)

and M151 (FRANK, 2018) to the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC). These cruises visited Atlantis, Tyro, Plato, Irving, Hyères, Great Meteor and

* Departamento de Biología Animal, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, E-29071 Málaga, Spain.

** Marine Research Department, Senckenberg am Meer, Südstrand 40, Wilhelmshaven, Germany.

¹ Corresponding author

Figure 1. Location map of the SASC in the NE Atlantic Ocean. Bathymetry data GEBCO, depth contours 1000 m.

Figura 1. Ubicación del área de estudio en el noreste del Océano Atlántico. Datos de batimetría GEBCO, isobatas 1000 m.

Little Meteor Seamounts (see Figs. 1-2). Some objectives of these cruises were to study the biodiversity and sedimentology of the plateau and slopes of the seamounts, and the ability of organisms to disperse from one seamount to another. Two previous papers deal with species of Seguenziidae and of the epitoniid genus *Papuliscala* (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020a, 2020b, respectively). The oceanographic and bathymetric context of the study area has been detailed there. HOFFMAN *ET AL.* (2019) studied three species of *Calliostoma* living in deep-water coral habitats in the northeastern Atlantic.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The methodology and data of the sampling area are detailed in the previous work by HOFFMAN *ET AL.* (2020a). The specimens are stored in the voucher collections at Senckenberg am Meer (SaM, Wilhelmshaven) and Muséum

National d'Histoire Naturelle (MNHN, Paris). Holotypes and paratypes are deposited in the MNHN.

Abbreviations:

Institutions: MNHN - Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle; SaM – Senckenberg am Meer.

Cruises: M151 – R/V METEOR cruise 151; Pos397 – R/V POSEIDON cruise 397; R/V – research vessel; SMT2 – R/V SUROIT cruise SEAMOUNT 2.

Morphology: H – height; W – width, maximum diameter.

SYSTEMATIC RESULTS

The family Calliostomatidae Thiele 1924 (Gastropoda: Vetigastropoda: Trochoidea) was first excluded from Trochidae by MARSHALL (1995a) and later reconfirmed as a distinct family by molecular studies (WILLIAMS *ET AL.* 2008, 2010; WILLIAMS 2012). Even though the family currently comprises

Figure 2. Map of SASC. Distribution of *Calliostoma cyrtoidea* n. sp. is indicated by red dots, *Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. by yellow triangles. Bathymetry data GEBCO, depth contours 1000 m. *Figura 2. Mapa de SASC. Distribución de Calliostoma cyrtoidea* n. sp. indicada por puntos rojos y *Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. por triángulos amarillos. Datos de batimetría GEBCO, isobatas 1000 m.

over 20 extant genera (CAVALLARI ET AL., 2019), the genus *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840 takes the lion's share in species and has long been a catchall genus for most calliostomatid species. In fact, all calliostomatids in the NE Atlantic remain today placed in this genus, historically based on shell morphology. A generic classification was proposed for calliostomatids from New Zealand (MARSHALL

1995a, 2016) and New Caledonia, the Loyalty Islands, and the northern Lord Howe Rise (MARSHALL 1995b); two sub-families, six genera and many new species were defined. Recently, TUSKES (2019) has studied the Calliostomatidae of the northeast Pacific and he recognized four genera in this area. A review of fossil Vetigastropoda by LANDAU ET AL. (2018) provided an excellent overview

of the calliostomatids of the NE Atlantic during the Miocene. QUINN (1992) provided the most complete review of NW Atlantic species, and DORNELLAS & SIMONE (2013) and CAVALLARI *ET AL.* (2019) reviewed the species of *Calliostoma* from Brazilian coasts. A generic revision of NE Atlantic calliostomatids is required but this effort is beyond the scope of this study.

DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1896, 1897) and DAUTZENBERG (1927) described *Calliostoma leptophyma* Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896, *C. normani* (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897), *C. grimaldii*

Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896 and *C. caroli* Dautzenberg, 1927 from the Azores. VILVENS & SWINNEN (2003) added *Calliostoma heugteni* Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003 from the Great Meteor Seamount. HOFFMAN *ET AL.* (2019) studied *Calliostoma bullatum* (Philippi, 1844), *Calliostoma leptophyma* and *Calliostoma maurolici* (G. Seguenza, 1876) in deep-water coral (DWC) habitats from the NE Atlantic. Most species in *Calliostoma* studied by DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1896, 1897a), VILVENS & SWINNEN (2003), and HOFFMAN *ET AL.* (2019) were encountered in the SASC.

Genus *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840

Type species: *Trochus conulus* Linnaeus, 1758, subsequent designation by Herrmannsen (1846).

Calliostoma maurolici (G. Seguenza, 1876) (Figs. 3-6)

Trochus (Zizyphinus) maurolici G. Seguenza, 1876: 184

Gibbula obesula Locard, 1898: ex P. Fischer ms.; vol. 2, 47–49, pl. 3 figs. 1–4

Gibbula maurolici: MICALI & VILLARI, 1991: 348–349, 360–362

Calliostoma maurolici: HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019: 101–104, figs. 21–34

Material examined: Atlantis Seamount - SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610–655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, two shells. Great Meteor Seamount - M151/23425-4, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 948 m, ROV sample, 25-X-2018, one shell (Figs. 3-6); M151/23429-5, 30.087°N, 28.727°W, 895 m, ROV sample, 26-X-2018, one shell; M151/23429-7, 30.086°N, 28.726°W, 902 m, ROV sample, 26-X-2018, one shell.

Type locality: Calabrian (Early Pleistocene) outcrop near Messina, Sicily. The type material of *Trochus maurolici* is lost.

Distribution: *Calliostoma maurolici* is common in deep-water coral communities in the NE Atlantic from the Rockall-

Hatton Banks off western Ireland to off western Morocco, the Azores and the SASC (HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019).

Calliostoma leptophyma Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896 (Figs. 7-11)

Calliostoma leptophyma Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 482 pl. 21 fig. 6

Calliostoma leptophyma: HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019: 104–106, figs. 35–43

Material examined: Atlantis Seamount - SMT2/DW254, 34.089 °N - 30.224 °W, 275–280 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW255, 34.082 °N - 30.255 °W, 335–340 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, six shells; SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610–655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, seven shells; SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795–830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, six shells; SMT2/DW265, 34.477 °N - 30.595 °W, 540–545 m, 02-II-1989, dredge, 10 shells, one live-collected specimen; M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, grab, 21-X-2018, one shell. Tyro Seamount - SMT2/DW277, 33.998 °N - 28.343 °W, 945–1000 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, five shells, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW278, 33.963 °N - 28.373 °W, 890–925 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, 19 shells; SMT2/DW279, 33.927 °N - 28.395 °W, 760–805 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, 21 shells, nine live-collected specimens (Figs. 7-11).

Figures 3-6. *Calliostoma maurolici* G. Seguenza, 1876. Great Meteor Seamount, M151 / 23425-4, H 13 mm, W 16 mm.

Figuras 3-6. *Calliostoma maurolici* G. Seguenza, 1876. Gran Banco Meteor, M151 / 23425-4, H 13 mm, W 16 mm.

Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW240, 33.205 °N - 29.032 °W, 565 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW241, 33.198 °N - 28.988 °W, 695 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.950 °W, 710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, 12 shells; SMT2/DW246, 33.232 °N - 29.602 °W, 520-550 m, 31-I-1989, dredge, one shell. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW208, 32.066 °N - 27.898 °W, 785-790 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW222, 32.347 °N - 28.262 °W, 1150 m, 27-I-1989, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW223, 32.327 °N - 28.433 °W, 800-995 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, three shells; SMT2/DW225, 32.143 °N - 28.178 °W, 1030-1035 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, four shells; SMT2/DW231, 32.025 °N - 27.908 °W, 745-750 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, 12 shells; SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1989, dredge, 14 shells. Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW184, 31.407 °N - 28.872 °W, 705 m, 15-I-1989, dredge, 3 live-collected specimens; SMT2/DW185, 31.425 °N - 28.863 °W, 950-1250 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, 4 shells; SMT2/DW186, 31.435 °N - 28.863 °W, 1520 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW200, 31.318 °N - 28.600 °W, 1060 m, 18-I-1993, dredge, 94 shells, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW203, 31.158 °N - 28.725 °W, 845-990 m, 19-I-1993, dredge, 38 shells, one live-collected specimen. Great Meteor Seamount - SMT2/DW158, 29.751 °N - 28.301 °W, 750-950 m, 12-I-1996, dredge, one live-collected specimen. Little Meteor Seamount - M151/23434-4, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 876 m, ROV sample, 27-X-2018, one live specimen in *Lophelia* rubble.

Type locality: Rocky ground east of Terceira, Azores, 38.52°N - 26.82°W, 845 m.

Distribution: *Calliostoma leptophyma* is common in cold-water habitats from the Hatton, Rockall and Porcupine Banks in

the north, the Azorean Seamounts in the west, Galicia Bank, Seine and Gettysburg seamounts along the Iberian margin, to

Figures 7-11. *Calliostoma leptophyma* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. Tyro Seamount, SMT2 / DW279, H 15 mm, W 15 mm.

Figuras 7-11. *Calliostoma leptophyma* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. Banco Tyro, SMT2 / DW279, H 15 mm, W 15 mm.

the continental slope off Western Sahara in the south (BECK *ET AL.*, 2003; ROLÁN & SUÁREZ, 2007; HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2019). In this study, shells were found in a bathymetrical range of 275–1520 m and live specimens at 540–990 m.

Remarks: The occurrence of *Calliostoma leptophyma* in coral rubble sampled at all locations suggests a close association with DWC habitats. The species displays a considerable morphological variability.

Calliostoma grimaldii Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896 (Figs. 12-16)

Calliostoma grimaldii Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1896: 480, pl. 21 fig. 4

Material examined: Plato Seamount – SMT2/DW250, 33.210 °N - 29.287 °W, 1450-1500 m, 01-II-1993, dredge, five juvenile shells. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW221, 32.297 °N - 28.255 °W, 1160-1180 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW222, 32.347 °N - 28.262 °W, 1150 m, 28-I-1994, dredge, two shells (Figs. 12-16); SMT2/DW225, 32.143 °N - 28.178 °W, 1030-1035 m, 28-I-1996, dredge, one shell. Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW200, 31.318 °N - 28.600 °W, 1060 m, 18-I-1993, dredge, two shells.
Type locality: East of Flores, Azores, 39.44 °N – 30.92 °W, 1557 m.

Distribution: NE Atlantic Ocean from the Reykjanes Ridge to off Cape Mogador: 31.7– 59.1 °N, 10.7 – 31.1 °W, 1030 – 2165 m. A specimen from the Manning Seamount in the Yale-Peabody Museum of Natural History (YPM IZ

028997, 38.16 °N – 60.67 °W, 1421 m) indicates an amphi-Atlantic distribution.

Remarks: It is the only NE Atlantic species with sharp carinae on a smooth whorl face.

Figures 12-16. *Calliostoma grimaldii* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. Irving Seamount, SMT2 / DW222, H 21 mm, W 20 mm.

Figuras 12-16. Calliostoma grimaldii Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896. Banco Irving, SMT2 / DW222, H 21 mm, W 20 mm.

Calliostoma normani (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897) (Figs. 17-22)

Turricula normani Dautzenberg & H. Fischer, 1897: 172, pl. 3 fig. 12

Material examined: Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW221, 32.297 °N - 28.255 °W, 1160-1180 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, two shells (Figs. 10-15).

Type locality: Off Flores, Azores, 39.18 °N - 30.40 °W, 1600 m.

Distribution: The Azores and SASC: 32.2 - 39.3 °N, 28.0 - 32.8 °W, 599 - 1600 m.

Remarks: The species can be easily identified by its large size (H 30 mm, W 32 mm), the slightly convex apical outline and fine and regular spiral grooves on the globose whorls (Figs. 17-22). *Calliostoma maurolici* is somewhat

similar but has a slightly concave spire and a coarser and more irregular spiral sculpture. *Calliostoma caroli* Dautzenberg, 1927 from off Pico, Azores, 1250 m, is another similar species; it has a coarser spiral sculpture with fine granules on the cords and a weak keel on the upper whorl face.

Calliostoma heugteni Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003 (Figs. 23-33)

Calliostoma heugteni Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003: 119-120, figs. 1-6.

Material examined: Atlantis Seamount - SMT2/DW254, 34.089 °N - 30.224 °W, 275-280 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW255, 34.082 °N - 30.255 °W, 335-340 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, three shells; SMT2/CP257, 34.075 °N - 30.251 °W, 330-338 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, one shell (Figs. 32-33);

Figures 17-22. *Calliostoma normani* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1897. Irving Seamount, SMT2 / DW221. 17-19: H 30 mm, W 32 mm; 20-22: H 30 mm, W 32 mm.

Figuras 17-22. *Calliostoma normani* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1897. Banco Irving, SMT2 / DW221. 17-19: H 30 mm, W 32 mm; 20-22: H 30 mm, W 32 mm.

SMT2/DW274, 34.086 °N - 30.226 °W, 280 m, 05-II-1993, dredge, three shells. Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW246, 33.232 °N - 29.602 °W, 520-550 m, 31-I-1989, dredge, one live-collected specimen. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW209, 31.986 °N - 27.933 °W, 435-460 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW215, 31.893 °N - 28.049 °W, 270-275 m, 27-I-1989, dredge, one shell. Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW182, 31.387 °N - 28.892 °W, 480 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW184, 31.407 °N - 28.872 °W, 705 m, 15-I-1989, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DE188, 31.499 °N - 28.992 °W, 300-310 m, 17-I-1994, dredge, 48 shells; SMT2/DW192, 31.465 °N - 28.985 °W, 700-750 m, 17-I-1998, dredge, one shell. Great Meteor Seamount - paratype 2 (VILVENS & SWINNEN, 2003; Figs. 29-31), 30.11 °N - 28.45 °W; SMT2/CP138, 30.032 °N - 28.472 °W, 300-310 m, 09-I-1996, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW143, 30.166 °N - 28.468 °W, 325-330 m, 10-I-2000, dredge, six shells; SMT2/DW147, 30.186 °N - 28.453 °W, 340-345 m, 10-I-2004, dredge, one shell, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW152, 30.033 °N - 28.368 °W, 470 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, 20 shells, 18 live-collected specimens (Figs. 23-28); SMT2/DW159, 29.738 °N - 28.349 °W, 330 m, 12-I-1997, dredge, four shells; SMT2/DW172, 30.085 °N - 28.692 °W, 455 m, 14-I-1993, dredge, one shell.

Type locality: VILVENS & SWINNEN (2003) indicated an erroneous type locality, where depth and coordinates do not match. Coordinates given for paratypes refer to the Great Meteor Bank.

Distribution: *Calliostoma heugteni* is widely distributed on the crests and upper bathyal slopes of the seamounts in the SASC: 30.0 – 34.1 °N, 28.3 – 30.3 °W, 270 – 750 m.

Remarks: For differences with other NE Atlantic taxa see discussion under *Calliostoma freiwaldi*. A similar W Atlan-

tic species is *Calliostoma militare* Ihering, 1907 (= *Calliostoma iheringi* Dall, 1927) from off SE America albeit that species is larger and has more convex whorls. *Calliostoma bairdii* Verrill & Smith, 1880 from off eastern U.S.A. is also similar but is larger, with a more depressed outline (apex angle 70°) and a closed

Figures 23-33. *Calliostoma heugteni* Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003. 23-28. Great Meteor Seamount, SMT2 / DW152. 23, 24: H 6.6 mm, W 5.7 mm; 25: W 4.2 mm; 26-28: H 2.0 mm, W 2.0 mm, protoconch W 0.42 mm. 29-31. Great Meteor Seamount, 30.11 N - 28.45 W, paratype 2, H 7.1 mm W 6.0 mm. 32, 33. Atlantis Seamount, SMT2 / CP257, H 6.0 mm, W 6.0 mm.

Figuras 23-33. Calliostoma heugteni Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003. 23-28. Gran Banco Meteor, SMT2 / DW152. 23, 24: H 6.6 mm, W 5.7 mm; 25: W 4.2 mm; 26-28: H 2.0 mm, W 2.0 mm, protoconcha W 0.42 mm. 29-31. Gran Banco Meteor, 30.11 N - 28.45 W, paratipo 2, H 7.1 mm W 6.0 mm. 32, 33. Atlantis Seamount, SMT2 / CP257, H 6.0 mm, W 6.0 mm.

chink rather than an umbilicus. *Calliostoma roseolum* Dall, 1881 from off eastern U.S.A., Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean Sea has convex whorls and lacks an

umbilicus. *Calliostoma melliferum* Cavallari & Simone, 2018 from the Canopus Bank off NE Brazil lacks the spiral cords on the base of the body whorl.

Calliostoma freiwaldi n. sp. (Figs. 2, 34-44)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 34-37, MNHN-IM-2000-35218), two figured paratypes 1-2 (Figs. 38-41, MNHN-IM-2000-35219, MNHN-IM-2000-35220), four shells (MNHN-IM-2014-7978), five live-collected specimens (MNHN-IM-2014-7979), all from type locality, SMT2/DW209, 26-I-1993, dredge.

Other material examined: Atlantis Seamount - SMT2/DW258, 33.997 °N - 30.203 °W, 420-460 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, 12 shells, two live-collected specimens; SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610-655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, six shells. Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW240, 33.205 °N - 29.032 °W, 565 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, four shells; SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, 49 shells; SMT2/DW247, 33.228 °N - 29.588 °W, 580-625 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, one shell. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW205, 32.018 °N - 27.953 °W, 348 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW208, 32.066 °N - 27.898 °W, 785-790 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, 10 shells; SMT2/DW210, 32.043 °N - 27.945 °W, 320 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, 17 shells; SMT2/DW215, 31.893 °N - 28.049 °W, 270-275 m, 27-I-1989, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW217, 31.892 °N - 28.051 °W, 270 m, 27-I-1991, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW231, 32.025 °N - 27.908 °W, 745-750 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, eight shells; SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, 304 shells, one live-collected specimen. Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW182, 31.387 °N - 28.892 °W, 480 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, 59 shells, five live-collected specimens (Figs. 42-44); SMT2/DW184, 31.407 °N - 28.872 °W, 705 m, 15-I-1989, dredge, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW188, 31.500 °N - 28.992 °W, 310 m, dredge, 67 shells, nine live-collected specimens; SMT2/DW190, 31.477 °N - 29.000 °W, 675-750 m, 17-I-1996, dredge, one live-collected specimen; SMT2/DW192, 31.465 °N - 28.985 °W, 700-750 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, eight shells; SMT2/DW202, 31.275 °N - 28.719 °W, 640-655 m, 19-I-1993, dredge, eight shells. Great Meteor Seamount - SMT2/DW145, 30.191 °N - 28.476 °W, 440-470 m, 10-I-2002, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW148, 30.200 °N - 28.410 °W, 585-615 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, two live-collected specimens; SMT2/DW152, 30.033 °N - 28.368 °W, 470 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, nine shells; SMT2/DW159, 29.738 °N - 28.349 °W, 330 m, 12-I-1997, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DE169, 30.065 °N - 28.645 °W, 310-320 m, 14-I-1996, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW172, 30.085 °N - 28.692 °W, 455 m, 14-I-1993, dredge, four shells.

Type locality: Irving Seamount, 31.986 °N - 27.933 °W, 435-460 m.

Etymology: The name is in honour of André Freiwald, a driving force in the study of deep-water coral habitats in the Atlantic.

Holotype, a live-collected and subsequently dried specimen (Figs. 34-37): Shell medium-sized (H 11 mm, W 11 mm), solid, glossy white, nacreous inside; spire raised and pointed with a slightly concave profile; whorls moderately convex with strong spiral sculpture.

Protoconch: nucleus with in total $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, surface covered by regular honeycomb sculpture with cells spirally aligned, cell size 0.02 mm, cell walls steep with flat top, thickness 0.003 mm. Lip curved, bordered by a weak rim, W 0.39 mm (Fig. 41, paratype 2).

Teleoconch: Spire slightly concave with $6\frac{1}{2}$ moderately convex whorls,

body whorl more convex than other whorls, rounded periphery. Apex outline angle 64°. First $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl with four rounded spiral cordlets and five varices. Next $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl with two strong spiral cords and a third cord developing on the shoulder area, and with about 16 coarse axial ribs with fine growth lines in the interspaces. Second whorl with three beaded spiral cords; about 16 beads per cord. Third whorl with three spiral cords with 20-24 beads. Fourth whorl initially with three spiral cords; 32-38 regular beads; fourth spiral cord emerging above suprasutural cord, which is separated from the suture by a concave channel.

Figures 34-44. *Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. 34-41. Irving Seamount, SMT2 / DW209. 34-37: holotype, H 11 mm, W 11 mm; 38, 39: paratype 1, H 9.5 mm, W 9.5 mm; 40, 41: paratype 2, W 4.8 mm, protoconch W 0.39 mm. 42-44. Hyères Seamount, SMT2 / DW182, H 13 mm, W 13 mm. *Figuras 34-44. Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. 34-41. Irving Seamount, SMT2 / DW209. 34-37: holotipo, H 11 mm, W 11 mm; 38, 39: paratipo 1, H 9.5 mm, W 9.5 mm; 40, 41: paratipo 2, W 4.8 mm, protoconcha W 0.39 mm. 42-44. Banco Hyères, SMT2 / DW182, H 13 mm, W 13 mm.

Fifth whorl, with fifth spiral cord emerging below first cord and sixth cord emerging below base cord; top and base spiral cords with fewest and largest beads; 32-50 beads on cords. Sixth (partly body) whorl with eight spiral cords with beads on upper whorl face. Base of body whorl slightly convex with nine spiral cords, more strongly beaded near periphery and near the umbilicus. Flat spiral grooves in between the four cords closest to the umbilicus. Open deep umbilicus with strong keel at margin, spiralling inside. No periostracum seen.

Aperture 30% of shell height, widely curved on labial side, columella flexuous, slightly concave at intersection with penultimate whorl. Lip sharp with corrugated margin reflecting external sculpture, bevelled inside, denticulate at the base (nine shallow raised markings) by termination of cords, prosocline, at about 40° with spire axis, flexuous at the base. A thin smooth callus covers rounded columella and parietal area. Inside nacreous, with external spiral sculpture showing through. Operculum spiral, translucent, light brown.

Variability: Outlines of adult specimens vary between clearly concave to nearly flat albeit body whorl is always slightly more convex. Some specimens show a spiral sculpture without beads on the base of the body whorl (Figs. 38-39). Adult height up to 13 mm.

Distribution: Upper bathyal range of crests and slopes of the seamounts in the SASC, 30.0 – 34.5 °N, 27.5 – 30.6 °W, 310 – 750 m.

Remarks: A similar species occurring sympatrically is *Calliostoma heugteni* Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003, which differs in having a higher spire with a straight profile, a concave columella, a

finer sculpture and very narrow umbilicus. *Calliostoma maurolici* (Seguenza, 1876), especially in juvenile stages, is quite similar but differs in having a more depressed outline and its beaded sculpture is limited to the upper spiral cords. *Calliostoma leptophyma* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896 has predominantly smooth spiral cords and a closed umbilicus. *Calliostoma melliferum* Cavallari & Simone, 2018 from the Canopus Bank off NE Brazil is also similar but this species is taller, lacks an umbilicus and the spiral cords on the base of the body whorl (CAVALLARI & SIMONE, 2018).

Calliostoma cyrtoidea n. sp. (Figs. 45-56)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 45-48, MNHN-IM-2000-35216), figured paratypes 1–3 (Figs. 49-53, MNHN-IM-2000-35217), 109 shells (MNHN-IM-2014-7967), two live-collected specimens (MNHN-IM-2014-7976, MNHN-IM-2014-7977), all from type locality: SMT2/DW200, 18-I-1993, dredge.

Other material examined: Atlantis Seamount - SMT2/DW254, 34.089 °N - 30.224 °W, 275-280 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/CP257, 34.075 °N - 30.251 °W, 330-338 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW258, 33.997 °N - 30.203 °W, 420-460 m, 02-II-1993, dredge, 27 shells; SMT2/DW263, 34.432 °N - 30.542 °W, 610-655 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 35 shells; SMT2/DW264, 34.412 °N - 30.513 °W, 795-830 m, 03-II-1993, dredge, 13 shells; SMT2/DW265, 34.477 °N - 30.595 °W, 540-545 m, 02-II-1989, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW274, 34.086 °N - 30.226 °W, 280 m, 05-II-1993, dredge, two shells; M151/23404, 33.971 °N - 30.206 °W, 677 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 48 shells (Figs. 54-56); M151/23408, 33.996 °N - 30.177 °W, 617 m, 21-X-2018, grab, 36 shells. Tyro Seamount - SMT2/DW278, 33.963 °N - 28.373 °W, 890-925 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW279, 33.927 °N - 28.395 °W, 760-805 m, 06-II-1993, dredge, 10 shells. Plato Seamount - SMT2/DW240, 33.205 °N - 29.032 °W, 565 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW242, 33.197 °N - 28.949 °W, 690-710 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, 55 shells; SMT2/DW247, 33.228 °N - 29.588 °W, 580-625 m, 31-I-1993, dredge, 28 shells; SMT2/DW250, 33.210 °N - 29.287 °W, 1450-1500 m, 01-II-1993, dredge, six shells. Irving Seamount - SMT2/DW209, 31.986 °N - 27.933 °W, 435-460 m, 26-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW225, 32.143 °N - 28.178 °W, 1030-1035 m, 28-I-1993, dredge, 5 shells; SMT2/DW237, 32.264 °N - 27.531 °W, 670-715 m, 30-I-1993, dredge, 26 shells; SMT2/DW238, 32.288 °N - 27.538 °W, 890-900 m, 29-I-1993, dredge, eight shells. Hyères Seamount - SMT2/DW182, 31.387 °N - 28.892 °W, 480 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, nine shells; SMT2/DW185, 31.425 °N - 28.863 °W, 950-1250 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW188, 31.500 °N - 28.992 °W, 310 m, dredge, one shell; SMT2/DW192, 31.465 °N - 28.985 °W, 700-750 m, 16-I-1993, dredge, five shells; SMT2/DW202, 31.275 °N - 28.719 °W, 640-655 m, 19-I-1993, dredge, two shells; SMT2/DW203, 31.158 °N - 28.725 °W, 845-990 m, 19-I-1993, dredge, 71 shells. Great Meteor Seamount - SMT2/DW152, 30.033 °N - 28.368 °W, 470 m, 11-I-1993, dredge, two shells; POS397/111-2, 29.750 °N - 28.466 °W, 292 m, 21-III-2010, Shipek grab, two shells; POS397/114-6, 29.683 °N - 28.434 °W, 289 m, 21-III-2010, Shipek grab, one shell; POS397/114-7, 29.683 °N - 28.434 °W, 289 m, 21-III-2010, Shipek grab, one shell; POS397/107-2, 29.804 °N - 28.433 °W, 295 m, 20-III-2010, epibenthic sled, one live-collected specimen; M151/23425-R6, 29.565 °N - 28.339 °W, 944 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, two shells; M151/23425-R9, 29.568 °N - 28.340 °W, 855 m, 25-X-2018, ROV sample, four shells. Little Meteor Seamount - M151/23436, 29.654 °N - 29.015 °W, 852 m, 27-X-2018, grab, two shells; M151/23437, 29.654 °N - 29.014 °W, 811 m, 27-X-2018, grab, one shell; M151/23440, 29.645 °N - 28.975 °W, 284 m, 27-X-2018, grab, one shell.

Type locality: Hyères Seamount, 31.318 °N - 28.600 °W, 1060 m.

Etymology: *Cyrtoidea* refers to the convex (dome-shaped) outline of the spire.

Figures 45-56. *Calliostoma cyrtoida* n. sp. 45-53. Hyères Seamount, SMT2 / DW200. 45-48: holotype H 6.7 mm, W 6.1 mm; 49, 50: paratype 1, H 5.2 mm, W 4.6 mm; 51, 52: paratype 2, H 2.3 mm, W 2.6 mm; 53: paratype 3, protoconch W 0.42 mm. 54-56. Atlantis Seamount, M151 / 23404. 12-13. H 1.5 mm, W 1.7 mm. 56: protoconch W 0.38 mm.

Figuras 45-56. Calliostoma cyrtoida n. sp. 45-53. Banco Hyères, SMT2 / DW200. 45-48: holotipo H 6,7 mm, W 6,1 mm; 49, 50: paratipo 1, H 5,2 mm, W 4,6 mm; 51, 52: paratipo 2, H 2,3 mm, W 2,6 mm; 53: paratipo 3, protoconcha W 0,42 mm. 54-56. Banco Atlantis, M151 / 23404. 12-13. H 1,5 mm, W 1,7 mm. 56: protoconcha W 0,38 mm.

Holotype, a live-collected and subsequently dried specimen (Figs. 45-48): Shell small (H 6.7 mm, W 6.1 mm), solid, white, nacreous inside; spire with cyrtocoid outline, flattened apex; whorls convex with strong spiral sculpture, suture shallow below suprasutural channel.

Protoconch: nucleus with in total $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, surface covered by regular honeycomb sculpture with cells spirally aligned, cell size 0.02 mm, cell walls steep with flat top, thickness 0.003 mm. Lip flexuous, flaring, bordered by a distinct rim. W 0.42 mm (Fig. 53, paratype 3). Transition to teleoconch clear by varix and change in sculpture.

Teleoconch: Spire cyrtocoid with four inflated whorls. Apex outline angle 75° . First $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl with five rounded spiral cordlets and three narrow, raised varices. Next $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl with only two strong spiral cords; upper cord at flattened shoulder area; lower smooth cord above suture; a third sharp cord emerging above suprasutural cord and about 19 narrow axial ribs, with fine growth lines in the interspaces. Second whorl with three sharp spiral cords and about 24 faint oblique axial ribs with nodules at intersections; fourth spiral cord emerging above first (shoulder) cord; base cord at lower suture smooth. Third whorl with axial ribs completely faded; fifth spiral cord emerging above fourth cord and sixth cord emerging below first (shoulder) cord; 32 – 38 strong nodules per cord. Fourth (body) whorl with six spiral cords on upper whorl face (at suture and above). Upper four cords nodular; the cord prolonging suture smooth and rounded with concave channel above. Eight smooth, rounded cords on convex base of body whorl, with irregular growth lines.

Umbilicus nearly closed by columellar callus. No periostracum seen.

Aperture 50% of shell height, nearly circular, concave at intersection with penul-

timate whorl. Lip sharp with corrugated margin reflecting external sculpture, bevelled inside, prosocline, at about 40° with spire axis, flexuous at the base. A thick smooth callus on rounded columella; pallial callus thin. Inside nacreous. Operculum multispiral, translucent, brown.

Variability: Juvenile specimens have a narrow open umbilicus, a funnel-shaped umbilical area, a flattened base and sharp peripheral keel (Fig. 54). While growing (Figs. 54, 51, 49, 45) the umbilical area becomes narrower and steeper and ultimately the umbilicus closes. A groove separates the columella from the outer lip on fully grown specimens. Adult height up to 7 mm.

Distribution: Upper bathyal range of crests and slopes of the seamounts in the SASC, $29.6 - 34.5^\circ\text{N}$, $27.5 - 30.5^\circ\text{W}$, 280 – 1250 m.

Remarks: The species was placed in *Calliostoma* because we lack critical information: the dried specimens do not allow analyses of jaws and radula. *Thysanodonta* Marshall, 1988 was considered but that genus is characterised by a unicarinate first whorl of the teleoconch whereas this new species has a bicarinate first whorl.

The species is similar to *Laetifautor fundatus* Marshall, 1995 or *L. trepidus* (Hedley, 1907) but these differ by a stronger axial sculpture and pointed nodules at the crossings with the spiral cords. More similar species are *Calliostoma spinosum* Landau, van Dingenen & Ceulemans, 2018 and *C. michaeli* Landau, van Dingenen & Ceulemans, 2018; these are extinct species from the Miocene in France. *Calliostoma spinosum* has a coarser protoconch sculpture and *C. michaeli* has a fine secondary spiral sculpture. *Calliostoma heugteni* Vilvens & Swinnen, 2003 and *Calliostoma freiwaldi* n. sp. from the SASC region have flattened whorls with fine spiral cords and a peripheral keel.

DISCUSSION

Seven species in Calliostomatidae were found on the SASC, two of which (*Calliostoma cyrtoida* n. sp. and *C. freiwaldi*

n. sp.) new to science. These new species, *C. heugteni* and *C. leptophyma* were collected alive. *Calliostoma mauro-*

lici, *C. normani* and *C. grimaldii* were only found as empty shells.

Most species of *Calliostoma* are carnivores feeding on a diet of sponges or on other sessile invertebrates (MARSHALL, 1995b). Scleractinians were encountered on all locations sampled in the SASC, many dead remains but also commonly live specimens. Other cnidarians such as hydrozoans, octocorals, and sea anemones were also commonly found alive in addition to many species belonging to different phyla. Therefore the SASC forms a biodiverse habitat with adequate food for deep-water carnivores like *Calliostoma*.

A wide morphological variability was found among the taxa in *Calliostoma*. The genus is in need of a generic review along the lines of the studies carried out by MARSHALL (1995a, 1995b, 2016) in the southern Pacific. A complete inventory of shell morphology, jaws, radulae and molecular data would be required to yield a new generic framework. We distinguish six groups in NE Atlantic species based on shell morphology: 1) "*granulatum*", raised conical outline, flattened whorls with strong spiral cords, some with beads (*granulatum*, *freiwaldi*, *heugteni*, *lithocolletum*, *hirondellei*, *occidentale*, *michaelit*, *gratiosum*†, *baccatum*†, *spinosum*†); 2) "*maurolici*", depressed conical outline, convex whorls with spiral cords, some with fine beads (*maurolici*, *cleopatra*, *leptophyma*, *gibbuliforme*†, *contractum*†); 3) "*cyrtoida*", raised cyrtoidal outline, inflated whorls with spiral cords (*cyrtoida*); 4) "*grimaldii*", raised outline, convex whorls with few strong carinae (*grimaldii*, *milneedwardsi*); 5) "*normani*", convex whorls with many fine and smooth spiral cords (*normani*, *caroli*, *miotumidum*†); 6) "*conulus*" raised, strong conical outline with keel and flattened base, smooth whorl face or with broad smooth spiral cords (*conulus*, *laugierii*, *gualterianum*, *dubium*, *virescens*, *funiculatum*, *zizyphinum*, *vibrayanum*†). Miocene species (†) were discussed by LANDAU ET AL. (2017). MARSHALL (2016) suggested that the NE Atlantic *Calliostoma normani* and

C. grimaldii may be related to his new genus *Phenacomargarites* based on their similar shell morphology.

The larval shell of all the species where it could be observed is similar to that of coastal European species. *Calliostoma zizyphinum* (Linnaeus, 1758) has been described (Lebour, 1936) as having a direct development, with the larvae developing inside a gelatinous spawn and hatching as crawling juveniles with the protoconch still in the honeycomb stage. The initial $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl of the teleoconch has a different sculpture but the signification of this is not known. Likewise, RAMÓN (1990) described the spawning, larval development and postlarval stages of the circalittoral and widespread *Calliostoma granulatum*. In this species the eggs are agglutinated into ribbons that formed amorphous clumps on the bottom, the veliger larval stage is short, taking place inside the egg membrane, and juveniles hatch as crawling young snails about four days after fertilization.

It is therefore surprising that species such as *C. maurolici* or *C. leptophyma* are able to bridge the distance of several hundred kilometres separating the SASC from Western Europe (e.g. the Galicia Bank, where they are known to occur also associated with DWC). Furthermore, the species that are possibly endemic to the SASC (*C. cyrtoida*, *C. freiwaldi*, and *C. heugteni*) are present on most of the seamounts, so are able to bridge routinely the distances in the order of 200 km separating those. The exact process used for dispersion is not known but instances in other groups (e.g. Rissoidae, GOFAS, 2007) indicate that direct developers are able to achieve more extensive ranges than could be expected from their type of larval development.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Crews and scientific staffs of cruises SEAMOUNT 2 (R/V SUROIT), Pos397 (R/V POSEIDON) and M151 (R/V METEOR) are thanked for their dedication in collecting the samples used in

this study. Nicol Mahnken is acknowledged for sample processing at SaM, colour photography and for preparing SEM samples. Bart van Heugten (NCB

Naturalis) provided a paratype of *Calliostoma heugteni*. We are grateful to the (anonymous) editors for improving our manuscripts.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BECK T., METZGER T. & FREIWALD A. 2003. *BIAS, Biodiversity Inventorial Atlas of Macro-benthic Seamount Animals*. OASIS, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, 118 pp.
- CAVALLARI D.C., SALVADOR R.B., DORNELLAS A.P.S. & SIMONE L.R.L. 2019. Calliostomatidae, Colloniidae, Margaritidae, and Solarie-llidae (Gastropoda: Trochoidea) collected by the Marion Dufresne (MD55) expedition in southeastern Brazil, with description of a new species of *Calliostoma*. *Zootaxa*, 4609 (3): 401-428.
- CAVALLARI D.C. & SIMONE L.R.L. 2018. A new species of *Calliostoma* (Vetigastropoda: Calliostomatidae) from Canopus Bank, off northeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa*, 4457 (1): 156-166.
- DAUTZENBERG P. 1927. Mollusques provenant des campagnes scientifiques du Prince Albert Ier de Monaco dans l'Océan Atlantique et dans le Golfe de Gascogne. *Résultats des Campagnes Scientifiques Accomplies sur son Yacht par Albert Ier Prince Souverain de Monaco*, 72: 401 pp., 9 pls.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1896. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse Alice 1888-1895. 1. Mollusques Gastéropodes. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 395-498, pl. 15-22.
- DAUTZENBERG P. & FISCHER H. 1897. Dragages effectués par l'Hirondelle et par la Princesse Alice 1888-1896. *Mémoires de la Société Zoologique de France*, 139-234; pl. 3-7.
- DORNELLAS A.P.S. & SIMONE L.R.L. 2013. Comparative morphology and redescription of three species of *Calliostoma* (Gastropoda, Trochoidea) from Brazilian Coast. *Malacologia*, 56 (1-2): 267-293.
- FRANK N. 2018. Short Cruise Report. M151. *Atlantic Thermocline Ocean and Ecosystems Dynamic during Natural Climate Change. Ponta Delgada – Funchal, Portugal. October 6 – 31 October 2018*. 15 pp. (not published) Institut für Umweltphysik, Universität Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany.
- GEORGE K.H. 2010. *Abschlussbericht POS397*. 16 pp. (not published) DZMB, Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven, Germany.
- GOFAS S. 1993. *Mission océanographique SEAMOUNT 2. Compte rendu et liste des stations*. Report not published: 1-30.
- GOFAS S. 2007. Rissoidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) from northeast Atlantic seamounts. *Journal of Natural History*, 41 (13-16): 779-885.
- HOFFMAN L., BEUCK L., VAN HEUGTEN B., LA-VALEYE M. & FREIWALD A. 2019. Last snails standing since the Early Pleistocene, a tale of Calliostomatidae (Gastropoda) living in deep-water coral habitats in the north-eastern Atlantic. *Zootaxa*, 4613 (1): 93-110.
- HOFFMAN L., GOFAS S. & FREIWALD A. 2020a. New and little-known Seguenziidae (Vetigastropoda, Gastropoda) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain. *Iberus*, 38 (1): 1-18.
- HOFFMAN L., GOFAS S. & FREIWALD A. 2020b. Ten new species in *Papuliscula* de Boury, 1911 (Gastropoda, Epitoniidae) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain. *Iberus*, 38 (1): 29-53.
- LANDAU B.M., VAN DINGENEN F. & CEULEMANS L. 2017. The upper Miocene gastropods of northwestern France, 1. Patellogastropoda and Vetigastropoda. *Cainozoic Research*, 17 (2): 75-166.
- LEBOUR M.V. 1936. Notes on the eggs and larvae of some Plymouth prosobranchs. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 20 (3): 547-565.
- MARSHALL B.A. 1995a. A Revision of the Recent *Calliostoma* Species of New Zealand (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Trochoidea). *The Nautilus*, 108 (4): 83-127.
- MARSHALL B.A. 1995b. Calliostomatidae (Gastropoda: Trochoidea) from New Caledonia, the Loyalty Islands, and the northern Lord Howe Rise. *Résultats des Campagnes Musorstom 14. Mémoires de la Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle*, 167: 381-458.
- MARSHALL B.A. 2016. New species of *Venustatrochus* Powell, 1951 from New Zealand, and new species of *Falsimargarita* Powell, 1951 and a new genus of the Calliostomatidae from the southwest Pacific, with comments on some other calliostomatid genera (Mollusca: Gastropoda). *Molluscan Research*, 36: 119-141.
- MICALI P. & VILLARI A. 1991. Le specie malacologiche di Salice (Messina) istituite da Giuseppe Seguenza. *Atti dell'Accademia Peloritana dei Pericolanti Classe di Scienze Fisiche, Matematiche e Naturali*, 67 (Supplement. 1): 345-363.

- QUINN J.F. 1992. New species of *Calliostoma* Swainson, 1840 (Gastropoda: Trochidae), and notes on some poorly known species from the western Atlantic Ocean. *The Nautilus*, 106: 77-114.
- RAMÓN M. 1990. Spawning and development of *Calliostoma granulatum* in the Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of the Marine biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 70: 321-328.
- ROLÁN E. & SUÁREZ M. 2007. Primera cita de *Calliostoma leptophyma* (Mollusca, Calliostomatidae) para aguas de la Península Ibérica. *Noticiario de la Sociedad Española de Malacología*, 47: 39-43.
- SEGUENZA G. 1876. Studi stratigrafici sulla formazione pliocenica dell'Italia meridionale. *Bollettino, Reale Comitato Geologico d'Italia*, Roma, 7: 179-189.
- TUSKES P.M. 2019. Calliostomatidae of the northeast Pacific. *Zoosymposia*, 13: 83-96.
- VILVENS C. & SWINNEN F. 2003. Description of *Calliostoma heugteni* n. sp. (Gastropoda: Trochidae: Calliostomatidae). *Novapex*, 4 (4): 119-123.
- WILLIAMS S.T., KARUBE S. & OZAWA T. 2008. Molecular systematics of Vetigastropoda: Trochidae, Turbinidae and Trochoidea redefined. *Zoologica Scripta*, 37: 483-506.
- WILLIAMS S.T., DONALD K.M., SPENCER H.G. & NAKANO T. 2010. Molecular systematics of the marine gastropod families Trochidae and Calliostomatidae (Mollusca: Superfamily Trochoidea). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 54: 783-809.
- WILLIAMS S.T. 2012. Advances in molecular systematics of the vetigastropod superfamily Trochoidea. *Zoologica Scripta*, 41: 571-595.